

**PHOTOVOLTAIC SUPERIORITY FOR SPACE STATION FREEDOM POWER
IN
THE 21st CENTURY**

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ABSTRACT

Complete power systems capable of delivering 75kW of continuous power in low earth orbit have been compared using current available data. Performance, liabilities, and advantages are discussed for a shielded nuclear system, solar dynamic system, and photovoltaic systems, both current Freedom Si design and near term GaAs/Ge with NaS storage. System components include power generation, storage (if required) heat rejection, power conversion and distribution, structural support, and shielding (if required). Performance parameters indicate the substantial advantage of the GaAs/Ge photovoltaic system without altering the support structure of the current Freedom design.

INTRODUCTION

The relevant parameters for comparison of space power configurations are (a) the specific power in W/kg, (b) the area-specific power in W/m², (c) the specific cost in \$/W, (d) reliability and safety, and (e) technology readiness. Caution must be exercised to fairly equate power systems by considering complete systems including power generation, storage (if required), heat rejection, power conversion and distribution, structural support and shielding (if required). Both beginning of life (BOL) and end of life (EOL) values are required for each parameter. Factors which influence these values include the choice of power system, the mission environment, the mission power level requirements, and the mission duration. The mission environment includes orbital data such as solar insolation, radiation environment, storage requirements, thermal cycling and also whether a man-rated system or radiation sensitive equipment are required. Entwined in the choice of the power system are also the heat rejection requirements and consequently the necessary radiator area. There are areas of power levels and durations which uniquely define a given power system and there are areas in which there may be a number of competitive power systems.

This comparison is limited to a Space Station Freedom low Earth orbit (LEO). Power requirements are assumed to be an average load power of 75kW. The radiation environment in LEO is primarily charged particles and is relatively benign compared to the ionizing radiation at higher altitudes. However, there are significant problems in LEO associated with the 5000-6000 thermal cycles per year experience by the spacecraft as it moves in and out of the Earth's shadow ($\pm 80^{\circ}\text{C}$). There will also be a need to store energy in the case of a photovoltaic array for a maximum period of 37% of the 94 min orbit cycle. Atomic oxygen degradation of contacts, interconnects, and materials used for the array structure also pose a hazard.

Area specific power, including illuminated area, radiators, and reactor shielding, is an important criterion because the added area produces drag in the residual atmosphere at space station altitude. The drag is proportional to the projected area in the direction of motion. For solar arrays, this area will vary as the array tracks the sun (1); an averaged area is used. At the assumed orbital altitude of 334 km., the amount of reboost propellant needed is about 4.7 kg/m² per year assuming thruster specific impulse of 450 sec., depending somewhat on solar activity. This can be a significant contribution to the total required mass to orbit. Drag becomes significantly less important as orbital altitude is increased, since air density reduces exponentially with altitude, reducing drag by approximately a factor of two for every 40 km increase in altitude.

The options discussed will be referenced to the Space Station Freedom power system for comparison. Technology development as required is assumed to be available within a 10 year time frame. The power systems compared are photovoltaic (PV) arrays and storage systems, an SP-100 shielded power system, and a solar dynamic system.

SPACE STATION FREEDOM

The current Space Station Freedom (Freedom) design is illustrated in Fig. 1. The space station power system for initial operating conditions consists of two solar power modules which will provide a minimum peak output power under worst-case conditions of 257.6 kW at beginning of life (BOL), 222.4kW at the 4-yr design point, and 206.4 kW at 10 years (2). A solar power module is shown in Fig. 2. Nickel-hydrogen batteries with a capacity of 259.2 kWhr provide power required during the eclipse. The batteries typically operate at a 35 percent depth of discharge (DOD), but are capable of an 80% DOD for a single contingency orbit.

Each solar power module consists of four solar array wings. Each wing is composed of two split blankets approximately 4.7 m x 32.6 m containing 82 panels with 200, 8 x 8 cm, cells per panel (3). A series string of two panels provide a nominal 160V dc output. The average efficiency of the silicon cells is 14.2% at BOL. The electrical design uses a large area 8 x 8 cm wrapthrough contact cell. The cell is 0.2 mm thick, has a gridded back-surface contact for added thermal performance, and is covered with a 0.125 mm thick ceria stabilized microsheet cover. The cells are mounted on coated kapton panels which are hinged to adjacent panels to form a

blanket. A 0.8 m diameter coilable longeron deployable mast between the blankets is used to extend the array and provide structural support. Array voltage is controlled at 160V dc. Four beta gimbals on each module provide articulation capability to account for seasonal changes, and each module has one alpha gimbal to permit rotation relative to the station axis. This permits the modules to track the sun during each orbit of the earth. The power system uses 160-Vdc electrical buses for the primary distribution of power and converts it to 120 to 126 Vdc secondary distribution power for the user interface. All power modules are compared outboard of the alpha gimbal which transmits the power to Freedom's feeders.

SP-100 NUCLEAR POWER SYSTEM

The generic flight system (GFS) presented consists of a reactor subsystem in which a controlled nuclear reaction produces thermal power at high temperature which is converted to electrical power (4). The reactor and power conversion subsystems are based on a 4 MW, reactor power level with reactor dimensions of 74 cm long by 55 cm diameter designed to deliver a net 150 kW electric power to the user for an equivalent 7-yr period during a 10-year total mission time (5). Fig. 3 shows the GFS Power System Configuration without man-rated shielding. A total radiation exposure dose of 20 rem was established for an astronaut's assumed 3-month occupation of the station. This dose consisted of approximately 75% natural background radiation and 25% reactor-attributed radiation. Human-rated shielding was designed to provide radiation protection for a projected set of normal operating activities and locations including on-station activity (habitat and laboratory modules), normal and emergency extravehicular activity (EVA), and shuttle orbiter approach, docking, and departure. The design compared here replaces the solar power module with a 100m boom extension and a shaped 4 π man-rated shield. The GFS design validation is not scheduled until 1995, after which there may be built a flight-rated system to fly by 2000.

At the end of useful life, the nuclear reactor must be boosted into a nuclear-safe orbit. This will require additional propellant, which has not been calculated in the specific power figures.

SOLAR DYNAMIC POWER SYSTEM

The solar dynamic system consists of a mirror concentrator, which collects and focuses solar energy into a heat receiver with integral thermal energy storage. A power conversion unit removes the thermal energy from the receiver and converts that energy to electrical energy. The concentrator is an offset paraboloid with a reflecting surface made up of triangular mirrored facets mounted in an 18 m diameter hexagonal frame. The overall concentrator will be pointed to within 0.1 degree of the true sunline. The solar receiver transfers thermal energy to the gaseous working fluid of the heat engine by means of integral exchanging passages. The heat of fusion of a mixture of salts is used to store a portion of the solar energy as heat for the eclipse period, eliminating the requirement for battery storage.

The power conversion unit (PCU) uses a heat engine based on the closed Brayton cycle using a mixture of He and Xe gases. Fig. 4 illustrates the closed Brayton cycle solar dynamic module. The mechanical to electrical power conversion uses a solid rotor three phase alternator located on the turbine/compressor shaft. The alternator electrical output is converted to distribution power by the power management and distribution equipment. Waste heat is transferred to a heat rejection/radiator system in a gas-to-liquid heat exchanger (6). The major concerns regarding a solar dynamic system are the pointing accuracy requirement, the lack of in-space flight testing to date, and the properties of the thermal energy storage materials operating in a microgravity environment.

SPACE STATION 21

The proposed Space Station 21 replaces Space Station Freedom's 14.2% efficient, 0.203 mm thick Si cells with 22% efficient, 0.076 mm thick GaAs/Ge cells (7), and replaces the NiH batteries (specific energy of 22 W-hr/kg with 80% efficiency) with NaS batteries (specific energy of 153 W-hr/kg (8) with 90% efficiency). The support structure is scaled to reflect the reduced array and radiator size. The cost and weight of the GaAs/Ge is assumed to be approximately the same as the Si cost and weight for Freedom. The power system would consist of two solar power modules, each consisting of two solar array wings. Each wing has four blankets, 25m x 4m, with 316 panels, each panel with 200 series wired 4cm x 4cm GaAs/Ge solar cells.

The GaAs/Ge photovoltaic technology assumed requires no new technology, but does assume advances in production and array assembly. Specifically, we assume that large area production CVD reactors will be available which reduce cell manufacturing costs to levels comparable to those of current Si cells, and that array assembly technology will be available to assemble the thin GaAs cells without excessive breakage and at no additional cost. This may require the cell design to be modified to a wraparound or wrap-through design for compatibility with the current array assembly technology.

The effect of the increased efficiency of the array, reduced cell degradation, charge characteristics, and heat rejecting capability of NaS batteries combine to substantially alter the calculated performance parameters. An example of the power distribution elements can be seen in Fig. 5.

POWER SYSTEMS COMPARISON

The mass of the power system components are listed in Table 1. Generation includes arrays with support, concentrator assembly and power generation subsystem, and reactor. Support structure includes beta gimbal assembly and interface structure assembly up to the alpha gimbal. Integrated Storage Equipment includes batteries, switching units, dc to dc converters, and battery support structure. Power Management and Distribution (PMAD) includes reactor instrumentation and control, cabling and power conditioning, control and distribution, where applicable, again to the alpha gimbal reference. Thermal Control includes heat transport and rejection. For the SP-100 reactor, shielding is man-rated for the conditions referred to in the SP-100 power system description. Drag area includes shield (9) and 100 m truss. The specific power and drag area specific power are listed in Table 2.

COMPONENT	SSF (75kW)	SD (25kW)	SP-100 (150kW)	SS-21 (75kW)
GENERATION (kg)	5765	4188	826	1881
SUPP. STRUCT.(kg)	1524	159	2068	762
INT.STOR.EQUIP (kg)	15502	0	0	2215
PMAD (kg)	637	233	1426	329
THERM.CONT.(kg)	7949	1676	1652	1944
SHIELDING (kg)	0	0	16950	0
TOTAL	31377	6256	22922	7131
DRAG AREA (m ²)	1077	208	303	456

Table 1. Power System Components

Power System	W/kg	W/m ²	Technology Readiness & Issues
SP-100 (150kW)	6.5	495	TB flight tested in 2000
SOLAR DYNAMIC (25kW)	4.0	120	pointing accuracy $\pm .1^\circ$ no flight data
SPACE STATION FREEDOM (75kW)	2.4 (4 yr point)	70	flight tested 1984
SPACE STATION 21 (75kW)	10.5	165	2000 production

Table 2. Power System Summary

DISCUSSION

The power system for space station Freedom is based on photovoltaic technology which is already ten years old. Considerable improvements are possible using more advanced technology. An improvement by more than a factor of four in specific power (w/kg) is possible by switching to high-efficiency GaAs/Ge cells and advanced batteries. This is significantly better than either the nuclear or solar dynamic systems.

End-of-life disposal of the nuclear reactor greatly increases the total mass of the power system. Assuming a disposal mass of 20950 kg, the propellant required to boost the reactor to an earth-escape elliptical solar orbit is 40000 kg (5). This reduces the specific power of the nuclear system to 2.4 W/kg.

In terms of drag area, characterized in units of area-specific power (W/m²), the advanced PV system offers an improvement by a factor of 2.4 over the baseline, resulting in reduced atmospheric drag and hence a lower requirement for reboost propellant. This is better than the solar dynamic system, but not as high as is possible with the SP-100 nuclear system.

CONCLUSION

With roughly the same technology readiness, it is clear that near term photovoltaic and storage improvements will yield great benefits in providing future space station power without requiring structural modifications. Deployment of the arrays on lighter weight structures currently under development (10) will further increase the advantage of a photovoltaic system. Discussing safety and reliability aspects also enhances photovoltaic systems' position as desirable power for future space station growth.

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Fig. 1. SPACE STATION FREEDOM

Fig. 2. Solar Power Module

Fig. 3. GFS Power System Configuration

Fig. 4. Closed Brayton Cycle Solar Dynamic Module

Fig. 5. Space Station 21 Electrical Power System